

Universidade Presbiteriana
Mackenzie

CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas
Programa de Pós-Graduação em Controladoria e Finanças
Empresariais

Implementation manual

Misstatement prediction model in construction
contracts accounting

Vinicius Pedro Toporcov
José Carlos Tiomatsu Oyadomari
Marcelo Daniel Araújo Ermel

Como referenciar:

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Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas

Linha de Pesquisa: Finanças, Contabilidade e Governança

Projeto de pesquisa: Earnings management detection

Produto Técnico-Tecnológico: Manual / Protocolo

Demanda Espontânea: higher transparency in project accounting

Organização:UPM

Descrição do PTT: Misstatement prediction model in construction contracts accounting

Divulgação da Produção: Congress, workshops and audit groups

Aderência Alta: Applicable in any company using construction contract accounting

Impacto Potencial Alto: Methodology can change the way auditors start their engagement towards project accounting auditing.

Impacto Realizado Alto: Model identify possible earnings management directly on real cases

Inovação Alta: no existing theory around construction contract accounting or earnings management in project management

Complexidade Alta: Development of own formulas and deep dive on linear and logistic regression

Aplicabilidade Alta: Tested through a database in an international company

Abrangência Potencial Alta: Applicable in most of multinationals company

Abrangência realizada Alta: Track-record of the models and the prediction in an existing and real databases.

Replicabilidade Escalável: Methodology can be transferred to other accounting fields of studies considering the prediction model

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Transformação causada pelo produto técnico/tecnológico no ambiente (organização, comunidade, localidade, etc.) ao qual se destina. Necessário declarar o motivo da criação, a relevância da questão do demandante e o foco de aplicação do produto. Avalia-se o impacto potencial e realizado do produto ao ambiente de transformação ao que se destina.													
Critério de avaliação	Realizado				Potencial				Replicável		TOTAL		
	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.		Descrição	Pontos	Pond.		Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Pontos	Pond.
IMPACTO (Peso: 25%)	Alto impacto	15	9,0		Alto impacto	15,0	6					15,0	25,0
APLICABILIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Alta	15	6,0		Alta	15,0	3		Escalável	15	6,0	15,0	25,0
INOVAÇÃO (Peso: 25%)	Alto teor de inovação	15	15,0									15,0	25,0
COMPLEXIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Alta complexidade	15	15,0									15,0	25,0
									Estrato	TA1	Pontuação		100,0

Impacto Potencial Alto: Methodology can change the way auditors start their engagement towards project accounting auditing. Impacto Realizado Alto: Model identify possible earnings management directly on real cases Inovação Alta: no existing theory around construction contract accounting or earnings management in project management Complexidade Alta: Development of own formulas and deep dive on linear and logistic regression	Complexidade Alta: Development of own formulas and deep dive on linear and logistic regression Aplicabilidade Alta: Tested through a database in an international company Abrangência Potencial Alta: Applicable in most of multinationals company Abrangência realizada Alta: Track-record of the models and the prediction in an existing and real databases.	Replicabilidade Escalável: Methodology can be transferred to other accounting fields of studies considering the prediction model
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Avaliação do Produto Técnico-Tecnológico (PTT)

O quadro 1 estabelece o somatório de 100,0 pontos referente aos critérios de impacto, aplicabilidade, inovação e complexidade. Assim, o produto técnico-tecnológico, relatório técnico conclusivo, tipo relatório de consultoria corresponde ao estrato TA1, conforme instruções da CAPES (CAPES -Ministério da Educação (MEC), 2021).

Para melhor documentar e apresentar os produtos técnicos/tecnológicos (PTT) elaborados pelo corpo docente e discente do PPG-CFTG, o NDE criou uma comissão composta de docentes permanentes, com o objetivo de analisar e recomendar melhorias quanto ao impacto, inovação, complexidade, aplicabilidade, abrangência e replicabilidade. Embasados no descritivo e nas justificativas apresentadas pelos autores do presente PTT quanto aos aspectos indicados acima (impacto, inovação, complexidade, aplicabilidade, abrangência e replicabilidade), os examinadores Octávio Ribeiro de Mendonça Neto e Ronaldo Gomes Dutra-de-Lima analisaram sua adequação e apresentaram sugestões de melhoria. Após a implementação dos ajustes sugeridos, os autores e os examinadores concordam que o PTT se enquadra na classificação TA1.

Modelo de previsão de manipulação na contabilidade de contratos de construção

Como referenciar:

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RESUMO

O modelo prevê a ocorrência de gerenciamento de resultados, mas na perspectiva interna da empresa, observando principalmente os contratos de construção gerenciados pelos gerentes de projetos.

O tema contratos de construção é uma prática contábil amplamente utilizada por empresas que prestam serviços de construção por meio de contratos complexos e de longo prazo a seus clientes. No método contábil em questão, as receitas e os custos são reconhecidos com base nos custos incorridos que possuem certo grau de discricionariedade, permitindo uma fonte de assimetria de informações que pode beneficiar o desempenho dos projetos e consequentemente os gestores dos projetos.

Consistente com as teorias relevantes de gerenciamento de resultados, os gerentes de projetos podem usar essa assimetria de informações a seu favor, como melhores incentivos, reconhecimento profissional e menor atenção aos seus projetos.

Este manual apresenta fórmulas sobre como calcular a contabilidade discricionária em contratos de construção e fornece um modelo matemático para prever manipulação nas finanças do projeto.

Palavras-chave:

Misstatement prediction model in construction contract accounting

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ABSTRACT

The model predicts earnings management, but from the company's internal perspective, particularly by observing construction contracts managed by project managers.

Construction contracts are an accounting practice widely used by companies providing construction services through complex and long-term contracts to their clients. In this method, revenues and costs are recognized based on the costs incurred, which have a degree of discretion. This allows a source of information asymmetry that can benefit project performance and, consequently, project managers.

Consistent with the relevant theories of earnings management, project managers can use this information asymmetry to their advantage, such as better incentives, professional recognition, and reduced attention to their projects.

This manual presents formulas for calculating discretionary accounting in construction contracts and provides a mathematical model for predicting misstatements in project financials.

Keywords: Earnings management, discretionary accruals, construction contracts

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Introduction

This misstatement prediction model can be applied to any project financials database and provides an accurate result for projects under construction contract methodology, with a high indication of current or future manipulation.

Its purpose is to be used by external or internal auditors and auditing committees to predict accounting misstatements in advance and challenge project managers.

The model development was accompanied by discretionary theory in construction contracts accounting: discretionary risk contingency, discretionary project costs, and discretionary project savings.

The model and the theory are unique trendsetters in earnings management from an internal perspective. They are also a venue for further studies in other accounting fields.

Contextualization

Companies acting in markets such as constructing plants, ships, equipment, factories, hydroelectric plants, power plants, and infrastructure projects use the construction contract method. It requires a complex offering of services that include the cost of goods and materials, the cost of employees, project management, etc., in a long-term relationship with customers and conjoint responsibility; such a situation requires a lot of special effort to transform the operational view into accounting.

It has a relevant number of management judgments and carries the previously mentioned information asymmetry (Beneish, 1997; Adeleye et al., 2013).

The earnings management phenomenon inside the company, happening among middle managers and those in charge of the statutory responsibility, should have equal importance in the earnings management field of study because it can distort financial statements.

Identifying internal earnings management would aid internal controls and audit professionals in developing mechanisms to mitigate information asymmetry and curb financial statement fraud. To avoid the dysfunctional use of management judgment, companies develop internal auditing mechanisms, which external auditors and the supervisory board then double-check. However, what is seen in the end are quarterly announcements covered by misinterpretation of possible future gains, poorly managed projects leading to earnings adjustment, and all sorts of poorly managed risks (Gleason et al., 2008; Desai et al., 2006).

Strengthening controls and improving the quality of financial analysis is an effective mechanism to curb misstatement and manipulation (Klein, 2002; Wongsunwai, 2013). The model also addresses this fact.

Objectives

- Identify project financial misstatements along the development of construction contract accounting.
- how the misstatement manipulation process occurs.
- The prediction of misstatements (earnings management) is made by considering the project's quarterly financial data.

Relevance

Internal and external auditors, as well as audit committees, have a powerful data tool to challenge construction contract accounting. The suggested prediction model delivers an accuracy of 55%- 78%, depending on the misstatement.

This may increase auditors' engagement and reduce the time needed to identify misstatements.

Shareholders with relevant stakes in companies using partial construction contract methodology will entrust more to the company's financials. This risk perception reduction will increase share valuation.

Theoretical Framework

Earnings management: Accounting earnings management refers to management decisions to change the accounting impact of events for their own benefit, such as bonuses, job safety, or pure vanity. Many countries and regulators are working on accounting regulation amendments to reduce accounting earnings management in favor of more transparent and value-driven accounting (Ecker et al., 2006).

Common types of earnings management according to literature:

- Big baths: New or transition managers use restructuring opportunities to be very conservative on cost recognition and accrual. (Dechow 2004)
- “Cookie jar effect,” over accruals aiming to make their life easier in the future (Dechow, 2004)
- Zero or minimal profit instead of loss: Managers avoid explaining losses (Beneish, 1997).
- Special events: Managers act opportunistically during special events, such as an IPO, secondary equity offer, or fiscal year-end, to boost share price or corporate bonus. (Burgstahler 1997; Skinner & Myers 2007; Soon Suk & Hyo Jin 2009).
- Beat the analysts: Managers avoid frustrating analyst’s quarterly earnings forecasts to maintain or increase the enterprise value expectation and earn-out bonuses consequently (Chu et al. 2019)
- Lack of control favors earnings management, especially when practices are accepted by superiors (Sayal & Singh, 2020)

Added theory

Construction contracts accounting should suffer from similar issues found in earnings management literature, considering the information asymmetry among project managers and the rest of the organization, including external stakeholders such as auditors and the audit committee.

The model adds the discretionary theory in project accounting, which is applied to three decisive KPIs in construction contracts accounting:

Discretionary risk contingency—A portion of the risk contingency that is not necessarily operational, which project managers use to steer project results. Risks are inflated, and reducing contingency leads to a direct improvement in the margin.

Discretionary project cost—A portion of project cost (excl. risk contingency) that is not necessarily operational and is also used to steer project results. The cost is inflated, and reducing project costs leads to a direct improvement in the margin.

Discretionary project savings are expected savings in projects that won't be realized. They are used to keep project margins stable. Reducing project savings leads to a direct worsening of the project margin.

State of the Art

The model is supported by advances in earnings management theory, which examines not only the build-up of accruals but also their release.

Dechow et al. (2012) unveiled a new approach for identifying earnings management based on the modified Jones model but with special consideration. In their opinion, it significantly increases the model's power to predict. The “build/reverse discretionary accrual model” is the first to use not only the variation of discretionary accruals as a test for earnings management but also the nature of its reversal. The model is based on the same empirical test from the modified Jones model that working capital accruals negatively correlate with cash flow from operations positions.

The model supports the development of theories regarding project controlling and construction contract accounting.

The approach developed could also be expanded by other areas of the earnings management internal perspective, such as cash-generating unit analysis.

Technical Product Description

Components

- Three new formulas of discretionary accounting were provided: discretionary risk contingency, discretionary project costs, and discretionary cost savings.
- Relevant construction contract financials were identified through linear and logistic regression analysis

The components described above are the baseline for the misstatement prediction, which interested parties can use.

Architecture

The project database should contain at least three consecutive project financials quarter information. Discretionary variables need to be calculated based on suggested formulas, with the goal of defining changes in project margin influenced by discretionary effects.

Project financials run in a logistic regression parameter. The aim is to efficiently predict misstatements in the three types of discretionary accounting.

Functionalities

- Prediction of misstatements in construction contract accounting using a project financial database with a short time series (3 quarters).
- Derivation of discretionary accounting under construction contracts.

Development Methodology

1. For each dataset, discretionary risk contingency, project costs, and project savings were calculated per the previously described models.
4. all quantitative variables were normalized by dividing them by the variable project revenue.
5. A Multiple regression was performed to identify variables explaining the three discretionary types of costs.

Benefits

Benefits are clear for Audit stakeholders:

1. Provide a theoretical framework for earnings management in construction contract accounting.
2. Digitize and accelerate the prediction of misstatements process.

Implementation Plan

Step one: Calculating discretionary accounting variables

Positive impacts on project margin quarterly should be divided into:

Changes due to increased price->ordinary business

Changes due to project costs -> discretionary project costs

Change due to risk contingency -> discretionary risk contingency

- The statistical model shows that 15% of discretionary risk contingency cases were from all data entries, while discretionary project cost was 29% of cases.

Negative impacts on project margin quarterly should be divided into:

Changes due to price decrease->ordinary business

Changes due to project costs -> discretionary project savings

- Regarding discretionary project savings, 36% of the data entries were affected.

Projects with positive discretionary values deserve a deep dive to identify possible misstatements.

This is a direct method of identifying discretionary accounting in construction contracts.

Conclusion

Any professional could apply three new formulas for discretionary accounting in construction contracts in an audit engagement and when at least three-quarters of project financials are available.

Considering the model's accuracy, project management will have less room to manage earnings within the projects.

Future Perspectives

Apply the discretionary accounting theory to other special accounting treatments, such as CGU accounting (cash-generating unit) or others where there is a perception of relevant management judgment as well as asymmetry of information.

Contributions

Discretionary accounting in construction contracts is a new milestone in earnings management theory. It adds the internal perspective and how control can be improved, as well as pitfalls from current accounting standards.

Business and academic accounting stakeholders are responsible for seeking improvements in current practices, and the theory presented here is an additional effort in this direction.

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